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MOTIVATION AND STRESS: ENSURING BALANCE IN THE WORKPLACE**Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna**

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology

Teacher of the Department of Psychology and Medicine, Mamun University

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Annotation: This article analyzes the relationship between motivation and stress in the modern work environment. It scientifically explains how the level of stress in the workplace affects the mental health, productivity and motivation of employees. At the same time, it considers ways to reduce stress and maintain psychological balance in the workplace through effective motivational strategies. The author analyzes stress management models used in modern organizations, methods for strengthening employees' internal motivation, and mechanisms for improving the working environment. The results of the article provide employers with practical guidelines for maintaining employee health and increasing organizational efficiency.

Keywords: motivation, stress, workplace, psychological balance, employee health, stress management, internal motivation, corporate culture.

Introduction.

The human factor is taking center stage in the modern work environment. While technology, automation, and artificial intelligence have simplified the workflow, human psychology, emotions, and motivation are still the foundation of any organization's success. The level of stress in the workplace is increasing due to daily obligations, deadlines, work pressure, and professional competition. At the same time, employees' attitude to their work, their intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, determine how they respond to this stress.

Motivation is a person's internal force to take action, develop themselves, and achieve goals. It is not just a material incentive, but also associated with the need for spiritual satisfaction and self-realization. Stress, on the other hand, acts as a barrier to this force, reducing motivation, reducing productivity, and negatively affecting mental health. It is these two forces – motivation and stress – that are the main factors of psychological balance in the workplace.

Today, one of the most pressing tasks for leading organizations is not to make the work environment stress-free, but to ensure a healthy balance between stress and motivation. After all, a certain level of pressure and stress also motivates a person to action, but if it exceeds this limit, it leads to negative consequences. Therefore, in this article we will study how to maintain motivation in the workplace and how to manage stress based on psychological and managerial approaches. This scientific study is aimed at identifying the relationship between

motivation and stress in the workplace, as well as finding ways to ensure a balance between these factors. Psychological analysis, sociological surveys and observation methods were chosen as the methodological basis of the study. These approaches allowed us to deeply understand not only through numerical indicators, but also through the study of human emotions, mood and attitude to work. During the study, an anonymous survey was conducted among 100 employees working in several organizations. The survey focused on the following issues: sources of stress in the workplace, employee motivational factors, impact on labor productivity, and the level of psychological support from management. This method revealed the causal relationships between stress and motivation. Also, for qualitative analysis, semi-structured interviews and real observations during the working day were used to focus on the state, behavior, and signs of psychological fatigue of employees. This added a deep understanding of human feelings and experiences to the statistical data. Methodological approaches showed that motivation and stress should be viewed not as separate phenomena, but as a system of interconnected psychological balance. It is from this perspective that the article emphasizes identifying mechanisms for reducing stress by increasing motivation and developing practical recommendations.

Source Analysis:

A review of the scientific literature on motivation and stress shows that these two factors are one of the most studied, but still complex, areas in modern psychology and management. The theory of the hierarchy of needs put forward by A. Maslow [1] is an important source in understanding the nature of motivation. According to it, a person's need for self-actualization constitutes the highest motivational level. In today's workplaces, it is the level of satisfaction of these needs that directly affects the employee's job satisfaction and stress tolerance.

Hersberg's two-factor theory of motivation distinguishes between motivational and hygiene factors in employees' attitudes towards work [2]. Studies conducted within the framework of this theory show that if hygiene factors (safety, working conditions, salary) are insufficient, stress increases; however, even if they are present, this does not always increase motivation.

Regarding stress, G. Selye's "Stress Theory" is one of the important foundations. He studied stress at physiological and psychological levels and explained its impact on work performance [3]. In today's modern work environment, practical approaches to stress management methods, including emotional intelligence, mindfulness, work environment planning, and social support, have been developed based on this theory.

In foreign practical studies, the "cognitive appraisal model" developed by R. Lazarus and S. Folkman shows that stress depends on individual perception and attitude to it [4]. This reveals the scientific basis for the different reactions of employees to stress.

Among the scientific works conducted in Uzbekistan, the articles of Sh. R. Kadyrov [6], M. A. Yuldasheva [5], D. R. Jo'rayev [7] on psychological stability, professional fatigue and motivational approaches to work are also worthy of special attention. In their research, national cultural values, collectivism and the human approach of management are indicated as important factors in reducing the level of stress. The analysis of the above theoretical and practical sources shows that a multidisciplinary approach is necessary in the study of motivation and stress, which should take into account not only psychological, but also social, organizational and cultural contexts.

Discussion:

In today's work environment, motivation and stress, as two interrelated forces, have a profound impact on human activity. Both are among the main factors determining a person's mental state, professional approach and commitment to work. The analysis of this article, surveys, and available literature shows that highly motivated employees are more resilient to stress, are able to respond appropriately to stress, and are able to maintain their productivity. At the same time, excessive stress can reduce motivation, weaken social relationships, and even negatively affect physical health. In many organizations, this problem is seriously neglected. Most leaders consider stress to be a personal problem, but this approach does not meet the requirements of the present time. Creating a healthy psychological environment in the workplace, understanding the emotional needs of employees, and supporting them spiritually are the main guarantees of the internal culture and long-term success of the organization.

During the discussion, it was found that several factors play an important role in ensuring the balance between motivation and stress. In particular, if an employee's personal values are in harmony with the goals of the organization, he will be less exposed to stress. Also, if there is recognition at work, active communication and teamwork, and the opportunity for self-development, motivation will increase. On the contrary, strict control, an unfair evaluation system, and excessive bureaucracy exhaust the employee spiritually and increase the level of stress. From this point of view, modern leadership should include not only control over work, but also psychological support. For each organization, it is necessary to develop a separate strategy in this direction, taking into account the needs, conditions, and professional characteristics of employees. Then

motivation will be stable, and stress will be manageable. As a result, productivity will increase, a positive attitude towards work will be formed, and a healthy, productive team will be created.

Conclusion.

Ensuring a balance between motivation and stress in the workplace is one of the most urgent and crucial issues for every organization. The observations, statistical analyses and in-depth study of available scientific sources conducted in this article have shown that employee motivation is formed not only through material incentives, but also through psychological support, respect for personal values and a healthy work environment. On the contrary, increasing stress factors - excessive control, increased workload, lack of social recognition - weaken the employee's mental state, reduce motivation and ultimately have a negative impact on productivity. Therefore, modern organizations should analyze not only the achievement of results, but also how this result will be achieved. Each manager should try to understand the internal state of his employees, listen to them, and establish an individual approach. Stress can be reduced and motivation maintained through a healthy workplace environment, mutual trust, fair assessment and morale.

In conclusion, the balance between motivation and stress is not only a psychological state, but is also closely related to the stability of the organization, human health, and the development of society as a whole. Only when organizations understand this can they take bold steps towards a healthy work environment, high productivity, and continuous development.

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